

Amino Derivatives of Selenium Monobromide. Part II*

Sarju Prasad and Bishan Lal Khandelwal

The amino derivatives of selenium monobromide have been prepared by the action of the latter on some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases. Properties of the derivatives have been studied and their structures discussed.

The preparation and properties of the compounds formed by the action of selenium monobromide on some aromatic primary amines have been studied in a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 645). The work has been extended to study the action of selenium monobromide on some aromatic secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases under similar conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Selenium monobromide was prepared by the method of Lenher and Kao (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 772); other chemicals used were of E. Merck or B.D.H. 'extra pure' quality.

General Method of Preparation.—Solutions of selenium monobromide and the respective amines were prepared in CS_2 ; the amine solution was gradually added to the former with constant shaking till complete precipitation. The product formed was filtered, washed thoroughly with CS_2 , and dried at the room temperature in a vacuum desiccator. Analyses and properties of the compounds studied are recorded in Table I.

Selenium was estimated as metallic selenium in a strong hydrochloric acid solution by reducing it with SO_2 . Bromine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method and nitrogen by Dumas' method in a Gallenkamp's electric furnace.

Properties.—The compounds formed with the secondary and tertiary amines and heterocyclic bases are in many respects similar to those formed with primary amines. These are generally coloured, amorphous, fairly stable, and practically insoluble in organic solvents. The compounds formed with diethylaniline and methylaniline are, however, hygroscopic and change in colour when kept in contact with moist air. These are hydrolysed very slowly in cold water, almost completely when boiled, and decompose when treated with dilute acids or alkalis.

On heating alone, the products furnish a greyish white sublimate, which is soluble in water; these are acidic and respond to the tests for bromine, :NH in secondary amines, and N: in tertiary amines. When these are heated with sodalime, the corresponding amines separate and condense in the cooler part of the tube, analogous to the behaviour of the compounds with primary amines.

The effective atomic number of selenium in these compounds is 36, which is a stable inert gas configuration and probably due to this the compounds are fairly stable.

The structure of these compounds appear to be similar to those formed with primary amines, as shown in Part I.

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* Part I: This *Journal*, 1960, 37, 645.

TABLE I
Compounds of selenium monobromide with amines and heterocyclic bases.

Amine.	Product.	Colour.	M.P.	%Selenium.		%Bromine.		%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
<i>N</i> -Methylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NHCH}_3)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Green	140°	29.82	29.69	30.18	30.08	5.35	5.26
<i>N</i> -Ethylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NHCH}_2\text{H}_5)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Dirty white	180°	28.29	28.21	28.50	28.55	5.08	5.00
<i>N</i> -Benzylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Greyish black	136°	23.16	23.09	23.47	23.37	4.14	4.09
Diphenylamine	$[\text{Se}_2((\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Bluish black	129°	24.23	24.08	24.28	24.37	4.34	4.27
<i>N</i> -Dimethylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Black	103°	28.13	28.21	28.49	28.55	5.02	5.00
<i>N</i> -Diethylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Dark brown	157°	25.59	25.64	25.81	25.95	4.51	4.55
<i>N</i> -Dibenzylamine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)_2\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Bluish black	123°	19.38	19.35	19.62	19.59	3.56	3.43
<i>p</i> -Amino- <i>N</i> -diethylaniline	$[\text{Se}_2((\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{N}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2)]\text{Br}_2$	Black	209°	24.32	24.45	24.67	24.75	4.35	4.33
Quinoline	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brownish black	107°	27.48	27.42	27.71	27.76	4.95	4.86
Piperidine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{N})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brick red	121°	32.49	32.37	32.70	32.77	5.80	5.74
Pyridine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Reddish black	135°	33.26	33.15	33.68	33.59	5.83	5.88
Piperazine	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2)_2]\text{Br}_2$	Brown	161°	32.35	32.24	32.69	32.63	5.69	5.71
α -Picoline	$[\text{Se}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N})_2]\text{Br}_2$	Pinkish gray	98°	31.39	31.35	31.65	32.73	5.67	5.55